

The Reality of Managing Sports Facilities in University Institutions.

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Abstract

The Object of the study aims to highlight the significance of sports management in enhancing the performance of sports facilities within university institutions, for this purpose, we used the descriptive survey method, On a sample composed of (05) administrators and (20) teachers at the sports complex, Chosen by a mass survey method, and for data collection, we used a tool the questionnaire, After collecting the results and having treated them statistically, we conclude that administrative management has a significant impact on the operation of sports facilities, that material possibilities have a positive role in improving the results of university sports, and that the incompetence of administrators has a negative impact on sports facilities, On this basis, the main recommendations are as follows Establishing additional sports facilities within university institutions, along with providing an adequate supply of sports equipment, Hiring experts in sports facilities management to oversee the sports structures within university institutions.

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1. Introduction

In the current era, sports have become one of the priorities of the individual's daily life, which the individual cannot do without. This great interest is due to several goals in the view of its practitioners. Some practice it for in today's world, sports have become an integral part of daily life, something many individuals consider indispensable. This widespread interest stems from various motivations. Some engage in sports for health benefits, others aim to reach higher competitive levels, while many participate simply for recreation.

Sports also play a crucial role in supporting educational and developmental goals, as involvement in physical activities fosters functional improvements, enhances physical abilities, and helps develop motor skills. Moreover, "sports have now extended beyond personal well-being, becoming intertwined with political and economic spheres" (Hadab, 2013, p. 12).

Sport is one of the most significant human activities, present in nearly every society throughout history. As civilizations have evolved, their approaches to sports have varied (Al-khouli, 1996).

Universities play a key role in nurturing athletic talent, supplying sports clubs with players across various disciplines, and contributing athletes to national teams. Therefore, the development of university sports is essential for discovering and nurturing talent, providing opportunities for gifted individuals, and organizing tournaments that showcase students' abilities. Any decline in university sports directly impacts the broader sports movement (Karoui, 2010).

To advance university sports, a clear and well-structured strategy is required, based on sound principles and careful planning. Achieving a high standard necessitates the availability of resources and capabilities aligned with international standards, particularly in terms of sports facilities. Effective management is crucial, involving the implementation of modern administrative functions and overseen by a team with specialized training in sports facility management. This approach must align with both the goals and aspirations of university sports programs (Hadab, 2013, p. 14).

Discussing the level of athletic performance among players inevitably brings attention to sports structures and facilities, which are the foundational elements in athlete development. In Algeria, these facilities have a direct impact-both positive and negative-on athletes' overall performance. To optimize the role of these structures, they must be managed wisely and efficiently, adhering to modern and sound management practices. The success of sports facilities in achieving their objectives largely depends on the competence and effectiveness of their management, as well as the principles guiding facility planning and resource utilization. The supervisor, being most

familiar with the facilities' needs, plays a critical role in decision-making and management (Zarwaq, 2020).

Due to poor administrative management, these facilities have faced significant challenges across various areas, leading to negative impacts on both the sports and the facilities themselves. This mismanagement has also extended to security and maintenance issues, and the lack of a clear management policy has resulted in confusion and inconsistencies in the inefficient use of these resources (Nadji, 2017).

Some researchers touched on previous studies, including, A study (Mirad, 2022), It aimed to at examining how sports management enhances the management of sports facilities. The researcher employed a descriptive approach using a survey method, which was appropriate for the study's objectives and nature. The sample comprised (30) administrators from three sports facilities in Biskra, selected through simple random sampling. The researcher utilized a three-axis questionnaire. The results revealed that sports management positively influences the management of sports facilities. Specifically, it highlighted the significant roles of planning, organization, and control in enhancing the management of these facilities. The second study is by the researcher (Hadab, 2013), It aimed to highlight the crucial role that sports facilities play in developing university competitions. the researcher employed a descriptive approach with a survey method. The sample consisted of (49) individuals, including (41) heads of sports activities departments in university housing, as well as four heads from the University Services Directorate and four heads at the university level, selected using a non-random, quota-based method. The researcher utilized a two-step process of questionnaires and interviews to collect the necessary data. The study's key findings revealed a significant reluctance among students to engage in sports within the facilities. It was determined that the lack of sports facilities in university institutions greatly impacts the decline of Algerian university sports. The primary obstacles hindering the development of university sports include ambiguous legal texts, an unclear organizational structure, a shortage of specialists, and insufficient budget allocation for university sports. As for the third study, the researcher (Bougherbi, 2005) titled "School Sports in Its Formative Aspect Between Reality and Hope". This study aimed to clarify the differences between the Algerian Federation of School Sports and the National Federation of School Sports in France. The researcher employed a descriptive method, which was suitable for the study's objectives and nature. The sample comprised (56) teachers from three states, selected through simple random sampling. To gather the necessary data, the researcher used a questionnaire with three axes and

conducted interviews. The results indicated a significant shortage of sports facilities and fields, which are essential for sports practice. Notably, the same location used for extracurricular sports activities often serves as the site for physical education classes, typically the yard of educational institutions. From the above, we ask the following question: What is the current state of administrative management of sports facilities within university institutions, and how does it affect sports practices?

2. Method and Materials

2.1. Participants

The research population consisted of all administrators and teachers working at the sports complex at Mohamed Khaidar University in Biskra, where they numbered (5) administrators and (20) teachers. The study sample also consisted of (5) administrators and (20) teachers working at the sports complex, who were selected using a mass survey method.

2.2. Design and Procedure

2.2.1. Methodology:

The researchers employed a descriptive approach using the survey method, which was well-suited to the study's objectives and nature.

2.2.2. Research variables:

- Independent variable: administrative management.
- Dependent variable: university sports facilities.

2.2.3. Research Scopes:

- **Human Scope:** This study is confined to administrators and teachers working in the sports facilities associated with Mohamed Khider University in Biskra.
- **Spatial Scope:** The research focuses on the sports facilities at Mohamed Khider University in Biskra.
- **Temporal Scope:** The study was conducted from the beginning of November 2022 until the end of May 2023.

2.2.4. Research tool:

The researcher used the questionnaire as a tool for the study.

- Validity of the research tool:

To ensure the validity of the tool, it was presented to a group of faculty members from the Institute of Physical Activity Science and Technology at the University of Biskra. A total of seven arbitrators were selected and asked to provide their opinions and suggestions regarding the appropriateness of the linguistic formulation, clarity, and relevance of the paragraphs. They were also invited to recommend deletions, modifications, or the addition of new statements, as well as to evaluate whether the statements were appropriately

categorized within their respective fields. The suggestions from the arbitrators were taken into account, resulting in the deletion, addition, or amendment of certain paragraphs. Initially, the tool comprised (18) statements for administrators and (21) statements for teachers. After review by the panel of specialized teachers, the final version of the tool consisted of (19) statements for administrators, organized into three axes, and (20) statements for teachers, also distributed across three axes.

- Research tool stability:

To ensure the stability of the tool, stability coefficients were calculated for all axes of the study tool, and for the tool as a whole, using Cronbach's alpha method. The sample sizes used were N=5 for administrators and N=20 for teachers. Tables (1) and (2) clearly illustrate the results of these stability coefficients.

Table 1. Reliability coefficients (Cronbach's alpha) for the study tool directed at administrators

Axes	Reliability coefficient (Cronbach's alpha)
The first axis	0.78
The second axis	0.84
The third axis	0.84
All axes	0.82

Table 2. Reliability coefficients (Cronbach's alpha) for the study tool directed to teachers

Axes	Reliability coefficient (Cronbach's alpha)
The first axis	0.75
The second axis	0.81
The third axis	0.78
All axes	0.78

It is clear from the tables that the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients for the dimensions of the study ranged (0.78 to 0.84) for the tool directed at administrators, and from (0.75 to 0.81) for the tool directed at teachers. These values are considered high and acceptable for practical application, as most studies indicate that a reliability coefficient of (0.60) is deemed acceptable (Amir & Sonderpandian, 2002).

Field application procedures for the research tool:

After conducting the survey and reviewing the initial version of the questionnaire, the final version was prepared and distributed to the study sample, which included administrators and teachers from the sports complex at

the University of Biskra. A total of (25) questionnaire forms were distributed, all of which were returned, allowing participants to express their opinions on the questionnaire items. Subsequently, the data and information were compiled, statistically processed, and analyzed to determine whether our hypotheses were confirmed or not.

2.3. Statistical Analysis

The researchers used the following statistical analyses:

- Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients
- Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study tool items and their respective domains.

3. Results

Table 3. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of sample members' responses to all axes of the study tool Directed to administrators in descending order (n=5)

n	The axis	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation score
1	Administrative management and its role in influencing university sports	2.4	0.27	1	High
2	The Role of Material Resources in Improving Performance and Results in Sports at University Facilities in Biskra	2.3	0.49	2	Medium
3	The inefficiency of managers has a negative impact on sports facilities and, consequently, on the level of students.	2.2	0.32	3	Medium
	All axes	2.3	0.29		Medium

The previous table indicates that the arithmetic means of the study sample's responses to the questionnaire axes ranged from (2.20 to 2.40). The first axis, "Administrative Management and Its Role in Influencing University Sports," had the highest arithmetic mean of (2.40), reflecting a high evaluation score. The second axis, "The Role of Material Capabilities in Improving Performance and Sports Results in University Facilities in Biskra," followed with an arithmetic mean of (2.30), corresponding to an average evaluation score. In third place was the axis "The Inefficiency of Managers and Its Negative Impact on Sports Facilities, and Consequently, on Students' Performance," which received an arithmetic mean of (2.20) and an average evaluation score. Overall, the arithmetic mean of the tool was (2.30) also corresponding to an average evaluation score.

The separate results for each axis are illustrated in Tables (4-6).

Table 4. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of sample members' answers to the administrative management section and Their role in influencing university sports are ranked in descending order (n=5)

n	The statements	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation score
1	Does administrative management have an impact on university sports	2.40	0.75	3	High
2	Do you think that the weak administrative management of university sports facilities leads to an impediment to sports practice	2.20	0.63	4	Medium
3	Is the management working on developing and Encouraging university sports	2.80	0.63	1	High
4	Do you have independence in decision-making in the administrative management of sports facilities	2.40	0.36	3	High
5	Does the management provide financial incentives Morale for students participating in university sports	2.40	0.68	3	High
6	Do you consider the competence of the managers who help you carry out your tasks sufficient for this	2.60	0.57	2	High
7	Are there factors that hinder your administrative management of sports facilities	2.40	0.51	3	High

The previous table shows that the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses to the questions in the first axis, "Administrative Management and Its Role in Influencing University Sports," ranged from (2.20 to 2.80). The highest mean was for the statement, "Is the administration working on developing and encouraging university sports" which received a high evaluation score. In contrast, the lowest arithmetic mean was for the statement, "Do you think that weak administrative management of university sports facilities leads to the obstruction of sports practice" which received an average evaluation score.

Table 5. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of sample members' answers to all statements of the axis of the role of material capabilities in improving the return and University sports results in descending order (n=5)

n	The statements	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation score
1	Where do you get your material or financial support	2.4	0.89	2	High
2	Is the budget allocated sufficient for the needs	1.8	0.83	4	Medium
3	Does your institution have the means and Equipment needed	2.2	0.83	3	Medium
4	Do you allocate part of the budget for maintenance and Renovation of sports facilities	2.4	0.54	2	High
5	Is the failure of university sports due to lack of financial resources	2.8	0.44	1	High
6	Can your budget support activities outside the university framework	2.2	0.83	3	Medium

The previous table shows that the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses to the questions in the second axis, "The Role of Material Capabilities in Improving Performance and Results in University Facilities",

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ranged from (1.80 to 2.80). The highest mean was for the statement, "Is the failure of university sports due to lack of financial capabilities" which received a high evaluation score. In contrast, the lowest arithmetic mean was for the statement, "Is the allocated budget sufficient for the needs " which received an average rating.

Table 6. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the sample members' answers to all statements of the axis of the inefficiency of managers, a negative reflection on sports facilities, and thus on the level of students, arranged in descending order (n=5)

n	The statements	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation score
1	Does the management have competent managers Qualified	2.40	0.54	2	High
2	Do you work on motivating and Encouraging outstanding athletes in these competitions	2.40	0.89	2	High
3	In the context of the tight management factor, do you organize and Coordinate with other bodies	2.60	0.54	1	High
4	Do managers perform their assigned tasks well	2.20	0.44	3	Medium
5	Is there a broad administrative concept Accurate management process for those in charge or supervisors of the administrative department	2.20	0.44	3	Medium
6	Does the administration retrain its managers through training courses in the country or internships abroad	1.40	0.54	4	Low

The previous table indicates that the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses to the questions in the third axis, "The Inefficiency of Managers Has a Negative Impact on Sports Facilities and, Consequently, on the Level of Students," ranged from (1.40 to 2.60). The highest mean was for the statement, "Within the framework of the tight management factor, do you organize and coordinate with other bodies" which received a high evaluation score. In contrast, the lowest arithmetic mean was for the statement, "Does the administration retrain its managers through training courses in the country or internships abroad" which received a low evaluation score.

Table 7. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of sample members' responses to all axes of the study tool Directed to teachers in descending order (n=20)

n	The axis	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation score
1	Administrative management and His role in influencing university sports	2.28	0.34	1	Medium
2	The role of material capabilities in improving the return and Sports results in university facilities in Biskra	2.18	0.30	3	Medium
3	The inefficiency of managers has a negative impact on sports facilities and, consequently, on the level of students.	2.27	0.51	2	Medium
	All axes	2.21	0.18		Medium

The previous table shows that the arithmetic means of the study sample members' responses to the questionnaire axes ranged from (2.18 to 2.28), reflecting an average evaluation score across all axes. The first axis, "Administrative Management and Its Role in Influencing University Sports," had the highest arithmetic mean of (2.28). In second place was the third axis,

"The Inefficiency of Managers Has a Negative Impact on Sports Facilities and, Consequently, on the Level of Students," with an arithmetic mean of (2.27). The second axis, "The Role of Material Capabilities in Improving Performance and Results in University Facilities in Biskra," ranked third, with an arithmetic mean of (2.18). Overall, the arithmetic mean for the questionnaire was (2.21).

From the above, it can be concluded that, from the teachers' perspective, administrative management plays a significant role in influencing university sports. Effective management necessitates the implementation of a management program tailored to facilities and resources to achieve better results. Such outcomes are contingent upon having highly qualified and experienced managers.

The results for each axis were also extracted separately, as illustrated in Tables (8-10).

Table 8. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of sample members' answers to all paragraphs of the administrative management axis and Role in influencing university sports in descending order (n=20)

n	The statements	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation score
1	Does the management of the institution give you complete freedom to manage the affairs of the team that represents it	2.40	0.75	2	High
2	What is your opinion on the current management system compared to the results obtained	2.25	0.63	4	Medium
3	Do you think that the administrative management adopted in university sports achieves the desired goals	2.25	0.63	4	Medium
4	What do you think of the cadres responsible for managing university sports	1.85	0.36	5	Medium
5	Do administrative managers work to meet the requirements of athletes	2.40	0.68	2	High
6	Among the repercussions of poor administrative management is the failure to exploit available capabilities	2.30	0.57	3	Medium
7	Do you think that poor administrative management of sports facilities is one of the factors behind the failure of university sports	2.45	0.51	1	High

The previous table indicates that the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses to the statements in the first axis, "Administrative Management and Its Role in Influencing University Sports," ranged from (1.85 to 2.45). The highest mean was for the statement, "Do you see that poor administrative management of sports facilities is among the factors contributing to the failure of university sports" which received a high evaluation score. In contrast, the lowest arithmetic mean was for the statement, "What do you think of the personnel responsible for managing university sports" which received an average evaluation score.

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Table 9. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of sample members' answers to all statements of the axis of the role of material capabilities in improving the return and University sports results in descending order (n=20)

n	The statements	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation score
1	Do you receive incentives from the administration when you participate in university sports competitions	2.40	0.50	1	High
2	Does the administration adopt scientific policies Modern and Effective in managing sports facilities	2.30	0.47	2	Medium
3	Do you think that the failure of university sports is due to the lack of financial resources only	2.05	0.60	3	Medium
4	Does the management provide you with the structures and Playgrounds for your business	2.40	0.50	1	High
5	What do you think of the possibilities available to you	1.65	0.48	5	Low
6	Does the administration support you with the capabilities when doing sports activities	1.95	0.51	4	Medium

The previous table indicates that the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses to the statements in the second axis, "The Role of Material Capabilities in Improving Performance and Results in University Facilities," ranged from (1.65 to 2.40). The highest means were for statements (1) and (4): "Do you receive incentives from the administration when you participate in university sports competitions" and "Does the administration provide you with the structures and playgrounds for practicing your activity" both of which received high evaluation scores. In contrast, the lowest arithmetic mean was for statement (5), "What is your opinion on the available resources" which received a low evaluation score.

Table 10. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of sample members' answers to all statements of the axis of the inefficiency of managers, a negative reflection on sports facilities, and, consequently, on the level of students, arranged in descending order (n=20)

n	The statements	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation score
1	Have you ever participated in university sports	2.30	0.75	2	Medium
2	Administrative management of sports facilities requires special administrative skills. Does the administration work on providing good training for its managers	2.30	0.63	2	Medium
3	Do you have the independence to decide which athletes participate in sports competitions	2.10	0.63	4	Medium
4	Are there any contacts between you and the presidents and University sports managers	2.30	0.36	2	Medium
5	What do you think of the prevailing management in sports competitions	2.25	0.68	3	Medium
6	management plans or programs Is this for the development of university sports	2.35	0.57	1	High
7	Is the role played by administrative management in developing university sports a good role	2.30	0.51	2	Medium

The previous table indicates that the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses to the statements in the third axis, "The Inefficiency of Managers Has a Negative Impact on Sports Facilities and, Consequently, on the Level of Students," ranged from (2.10 to 2.35). The highest mean was for statement (6), "Does the administration follow management plans or programs to develop university sports" which received a high evaluation score. Conversely, the lowest arithmetic average was for statement (3), "Do you have the independence to decide which athletes participate in sports competitions" which received an average rating.

4. Discussion

The results in Table (4) indicate that the administration is actively working to develop and encourage university sports. It is evident that effective and successful management positively impacts sports development; conversely, weak management can significantly hinder progress and lead to failure in achieving objectives. As noted by (Ibrahim, 2002), sports, like other aspects of life, require effective management and organization. Specialists in sports management have presented theoretical concepts and processes that align with practical applications. Their roles involve analysis, planning, reporting, and monitoring essential daily issues related to the development of physical education and sports, drawing on accumulated administrative experience. The findings of this study align with those of (Mirad, 2022), which indicated that sports management plays a positive role in enhancing the management of sports facilities.

From Table (5) It can be concluded that the lack of financial resources is a significant issue facing sports in general, and university sports are negatively impacted by this problem. This situation arises from insufficient interest and support, which results in the budget being unable to cover all related activities as well as those outside its scope. The findings of this study align with those of (Hadab, 2013), which indicated a shortage in the budget allocated to university sports.

From Table (6), we can conclude that this administration effectively coordinates with other relevant bodies, allowing it to broaden its scope of practice and engage in various sports activities. This aligns with the tight management factor. However, we found a lack of interest in retraining the personnel responsible for administrative management, which negatively impacts the facilities and sports overall. The findings of this study are somewhat similar to those of (Hadab, 2013), which indicated a lack of specialists in the field of sports management.

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From Table (8), we can conclude that poor administrative management contributes to the failure of university sports. This inadequacy is largely attributed to a lack of qualified and specialized personnel across various fields. Conversely, effective administrative management plays a crucial role in the development of university sports. The findings of this study are somewhat similar to those of (Hadab, 2013), which indicated a notable absence of specialists in the field of sports management.

From Table (9), it can be said that the university institution attaches great importance to the structural aspects and facilities for practicing sports activities, as it offers a variety of stadiums and halls equipped with modern equipment. Additionally, the administration provides the necessary equipment for teachers when they participate in university sports competitions. Regarding capabilities, we conclude that some facilities possess reasonable resources that support the practice of physical activity to a significant extent, though others may not be suitable and require maintenance. As noted by (Abdul-Maqsoud & Al-shafei, 2003), the budget allocated for sports activities must be adequate to allow the implementation of programs per the institution's approved goals. The results of this study differ from those of (Bougharbi, 2005), which indicated a significant shortage of sports facilities and fields that are considered essential for sports practice. In Bougharbi's study, it was found that the location for school sports activities often doubled as the space for physical education classes, typically confined to the yards of educational institutions.

Organization and planning are crucial in all fields. And from Table (10), we can conclude that these facilities depend on organizational plans in their management processes, which contributes to the development of university sports. However, it appears that the management of this institution does not grant full autonomy to teachers in executing their responsibilities related to university sports, as it adheres to well-structured organizational programs and plans. As noted by (Al-Tayeb, 2006), a manager is someone who can perform work and accomplish tasks through others. This individual acts as a planner, activator, organizer, monitor, and coordinator of collective efforts to achieve a common goal. Therefore, the manager is accountable for the work of others and must possess a certain level of researchers to make decisions; otherwise, they risk losing their managerial status and becoming merely an executor of tasks. The findings of this study align somewhat with those of (Mirad, 2022), whose research indicated that planning plays a vital role in enhancing the management of sports facilities, and that organization is also significant in improving management practices in this context.

5. Conclusion

Through this study, we sought to uncover the reality of the management of sports facilities within the university institution. After the field study, we came up with the following findings:

- Administrative management significantly affects sports facilities, which in turn impacts sports practice.
- Financial capabilities are crucial for enhancing the return on and results of university sports.
- The inefficiency of managers negatively influences both sports facilities and student engagement.

Based on these findings, we propose the following suggestions:

- Establishing additional sports facilities within university institutions, along with providing an adequate supply of sports equipment.
- Involving university sports supervisors—including specialists, technicians, and administrators—in the design and construction of facilities across various university institutions.
- Hiring experts in sports facilities management to oversee the sports structures within university institutions.
- Organizing training and development courses for supervisors and staff managing sports facilities, in collaboration with specialists in management and sports administration.
- Enhancing the role of departments responsible for sports activities within university institutions to attract more students to participate in their desired sports, thereby serving as a talent pool for university sports at both local and national levels.

References

- Abdul-Maqsoud, I. M., & Al-shafei, H. A. (2003). *The Scientific Encyclopedia of Sports Management - Planning in the sports field* . Egypt: Dar Al-Wafa for Printing and Publishing.
- Al-khouli, A. A. (1996). *Sports and Society* . Kuwait : National Council for Culture Arts and Letters .
- Al-Tayeb, M. R. (2006). *Introduction to management: Basics - functions - Techniques*. Algeria : Office of University publications .
- Amir, D., & Sonderpandian, J. (2002). *Complete business statistics* . New York : Mc Graw Hill.
- Bougharbi, M. (2005). Algerian school sports in their formative aspect between reality and hope. Institute of physical Education and sports , Algeria : University of Algiers .
- Hadab, S. (2013). An analytical study of the reality of Algerian university sports in light of the management of its sports facilities. Institute of physical Education and sports, Algeria: University of Algiers 3.
- Ibrahim, M. A. (2002). *Management of sports Championships and Competitions* . Jordan : Dar Al thaqafa for publishing and Distribution .
- Karoui, R. A. (2010). The reality of sports championships at Al-Qadisiyah University and ways to develop them. *Al-Qadisiyah journal of sports Education Sciences* , 10(2), 185-202.
- Mirad, E. (2022). The role of sports management in managing sports facilities. Institute of Sciences and Technologies of physical and sports Activities , Algeria : University mohamed khider .
- Nadji, Y. (2017). The role of administrative management in the sports facility and its impact on sports practice from the point of view of beneficiaries. Institute of Sciences and Technologies of physical and sports Activities , Algeria : University Mohamed Khider .
- Zarwaq, H. (2020). Obstacles to Sustainable Development in the Management of Sports Facilities. Institute of Sciences and Technologies of Physical and Sports Activities , Algeria : University of Msila .